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IN ANESTHESIOLOGY
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POST-INTENSIVE CARE SYNDROME – ANAESTHESIOLOGISTS “NIGHTMARE”

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Introduction

PICS is now being recognized as a public health burden due to the associated neuropsychological and functional disability, however its exact prevalence remains unknown. It has been reported to occur on average in 25% of ICU survivors, but few studies have shown its incidence to be significantly high, occurring in more than 3/4th of ICU survivors¹. The major risk factors associated with it are duration of delirium in ICU, acute brain dysfunction (stroke, alcoholism), hypoxia (ARDS, cardiac arrest), hypotension (severe sepsis, trauma), glucose dysregulation, respiratory failure requiring prolonged mechanical ventilation, severe sepsis, use of renal replacement therapy, and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), prior cognitive impairment (older age, preexisting cognitive deficits, premorbid health conditions)¹⁻¹⁰.

What is Post-Intensive Care Syndrome?

Intensive care can affect a person's body, thoughts, feelings, mind and interactions with friends or family. This is referred to as post-intensive care syndrome, or PICS. It can be as obvious as weakened muscles, or less obvious like problems with thinking and judgment, depression or anxiety. The risk that your loved one may experience PICS increases if they:

- Were in the ICU longer than three to five days.
- Have an infection or sepsis that needs daily care.
- Multiple affected organs like their lungs, kidney, skin, heart, brain or others.
- Need a mechanical ventilator to help them breathe.
- Weakness from degenerated nerves and muscle.
- Poor nutrition.
- Trouble with attention, memory or reasoning.
- Post-traumatic stress disorder symptoms with frightening memories or hallucinations¹⁻¹⁹.

What are the risk factors?

The risk factors for developing PICS have yet to be fully defined. At this time, illness requiring admission to an Intensive Care Unit (ICU) and development of delirium during the ICU stay are the two risk factors most closely associated with risk for developing PICS. Other risk factors thought to contribute to the development of PICS include: mechanical ventilation during the ICU stay, older age, ICU stay >48 hours, a diagnosis of sepsis, and use of sedative medications. As our overall knowledge of PICS expands, so will our understanding of what places our patients at risk for this syndrome²⁻⁶.

How is PICS diagnosed?

There is no one specific test used to diagnose PICS. This syndrome is diagnosed based on the patient's history of critical illness and the development of new or worsening impairments of cognitive, mental, and/or physical functioning following the critical illness. Because this syndrome typically develops following discharge from the ICU, it is usually recognized by non-ICU healthcare providers and/or the patient's primary care provider³⁻⁸.

What are the signs and symptoms of PICS?

As the definition of PICS highlights, this syndrome can affect one or several aspects of a person's life. The mental, physical, and cognitive affects are highlighted below.

- Body: Muscles weakness, difficulty with balance
- Thoughts/Feelings: Anxiety, depression, sleep disturbance, nightmares
- Mind: Problems with thinking, problems with memory, difficulty concentrating, difficulty completing daily tasks⁸⁻¹¹.

How is PICS prevented?

This includes but is not limited to ICU interventions such as:

- Ensuring quality sleep.
- Preventing the development of delirium.
- Limiting the amount of medications used to sedate patients.
- Limiting the need for and length of mechanical ventilation.
- Getting patients up, out of bed, and mobile as early as possible during their ICU stay.
- Encouraging daily journaling while in the ICU by patients, caregivers, and/or family¹²⁻⁵.

What can be done to treat PICS?

Treatment of PICS depends on the area of function affected by the condition. Discussion with the patient and family during hospitalization can help identify potential problems early. ICU follow up may also play a vital role in identifying. Appropriate post-ICU experts may be needed to provide support.

Post-intensive care syndrome (PICS) describes the disability that remains in the surviving the critical illness. This comprises of impairment in cognition, psychological health, and physical function of the intensive care unit

(ICU) survivor.^{1,2} Consequent to this, the psychological health of family members of the survivor may also be affected in an adverse manner, termed as PICS-Family (PICS-F).^{1,2} It has been observed that up to 30% of family or the caregivers experience stress, anxiety, depression, and complicated grief²⁻¹⁶.

Prevention and management

All patients being admitted into the ICU facility should undergo a psychological evaluation that includes: (a) preadmission history, (b) ability to adapt to stress in past, (c) medication history, (d) current mental and clinical status, and (e) environmental and family factors. The treatment of the ICU syndrome includes: (a) the elimination or correction of causative factors, (b) the appropriate administration of sedatives (anxiolytic and antipsychotic agents), (c) reduction or elimination of sources of environmental stress, and (d) frequent patient and family communication¹⁻¹⁹.

Conclusions

The ABCDE bundle has been used with good preventive rates for PICS. This comprises of:

- Awakening (using light or minimal sedation);
- Breathing (spontaneous breathing trials);
- Coordination of care and communication among various disciplines;
- Delirium monitoring, assessment, and management;
- Early ambulation in the ICU.

Additional interventions to prevent PICS include: (1) Avoiding hypoglycemia and hypoxemia. (2) ICU diaries: Maintenance of ICU diary prospectively by the family members, health care providers, or both during the patient's ICU stay.

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